

Kinetics and mechanism of the interaction of bio-active ligands with *cis*-diaqua-bis(bipyridyl)ruthenium(II) in aqueous medium

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Abstract : The interaction of the title complex with thioglycolic acid and 2-thiouracil has been studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous medium as a function of [substrate complex], [ligand] and temperature. The reaction has been monitored at 480 nm where the spectral difference between the reactant and product is a maximum. At pH 4.5, the reaction has been found to proceed via two distinct consecutive steps i.e. it shows a non-linear dependence on the concentration of ligands : first process is [ligand] dependent but the second step is [ligand] independent. The rate constants for the processes are : $k_1 \sim 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 \sim 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The activation parameters were calculated from Eyring plots. Based on the kinetic and activation parameters, an associative interchange mechanism is proposed for the interaction processes. From the temperature dependence of the outer sphere association equilibrium constant, the thermodynamic parameters were also calculated. The product of the reaction has been characterized by IR and ESI-mass spectroscopic analysis.

Keywords : Kinetics, ligand substitution, ruthenium(II), thioglycolic acid, 2-thiouracil.

Introduction

The substitution reactions of ruthenium(II/III) complexes are well studied¹⁻⁹. Previous studies on the nucleophilic substitution reaction of *cis*-diaqua-bis(bipyridyl)-ruthenium(II) complex ion, $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$, show that no single mechanism can explain these reactions. Substitution reactions of ruthenium(II/III) complexes follow both associative and dissociative mechanism depending on nature of the ligand and reaction conditions. The ruthenium complexes of 2,2'-bipyridine and its substituted derivatives are the only known examples of chelate nitrogen complexes of ruthenium for many years.

Ruthenium complexes have considerable antibacterial power like other platinum, rhodium and palladium complexes^{10,11}. Of them ruthenium complexes are less toxic^{12,13} than other complexes. Ruthenium complexes are also of interest because of their anti HIV¹⁴, anticancer¹⁵, anti-leukemic¹⁶, antifungal¹⁷ and DNA binding¹⁸ activities. Ruthenium complexes also have photochemical and redox activities.

Small bioactive molecules, namely 2-thiouracil and thioglycolic acid, were chosen for the current kinetic studies. The sulfur-containing compound 2-thiouracil is a com-

ponent in certain nucleic acids and is also a minor component of transfer ribonucleic acid (tRNA). For example, 2-thiouracil has been characterized in tRNA^{Glu} isolated from *Escherichia coli*¹⁹. The ability of thioglycolic acid to mimic many biological molecules, like thiol containing proteins and peptides in binding to ruthenium complex is well known¹⁹.

Most of the well-known platinum anticancer complexes have the general formula *cis*-[Pt(NHR₂)₂X₂]. The biological activity associated with cisplatin type compounds is normally associated with the presence of two fairly labile *cis* ligand, e.g. the two chloro groups in cisplatin. Testing of these complexes for antitumor activity showed that only the *cis* isomer displayed anticancer activity, while the *trans* did not¹⁹. *cis*-[Ru(bipy)₂(H₂O)₂]²⁺ isomer is chosen for the studies described in the present paper as a representative of platinum drugs.

A number of studies have been done on this very novel system; but the biphasic nature of this system in its kinetic behavior is only recently explored⁶. In this article we have discussed the kinetic aspects of the substitution of aqua molecules from *cis*-diaqua-bis(bipyridyl)-ruthenium(II) complex by thioglycolic acid and 2-thio-

uracil in aqueous medium. The study is important both from kinetic aspects and from biological aspects.

Experimental

The compound $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2\text{CO}_3]2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by Meyer's method²⁰ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ (1) was prepared *in situ* by acidification of the above complexes with *p*-toluene sulfonic acid. The pH of the solution was adjusted by adding *p*-toluene sulfonic acid/NaOH and maintained in the acidic region to prevent the oxidation of Ru^{II} to Ru^{III} ²¹. The ionic strength of the reaction medium was adjusted with sodium salt of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid and pH adjustments were done with the help of a Sartorius digital pH meter (model PB-11). A typical kinetic run was given using acetate as a ligand to confirm that acetate would not act as a ligand; and thus acetate buffer was used to maintain the pHs of the reaction mixtures. The reaction products (2) and (3) were prepared from the reaction of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ with thioglycolic acid (tgaH_2) and 2-thiouracil (tuc) respectively on mixing the reactants in 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 1 : 5 and 1 : 10 ratios and thermostated at 50 °C for 72 h. The λ_{max} values for complex 1, 2 and 3 are 482, 415 and 489 nm respectively. The complete complexation by the ligands was indicated by the almost same absorbances at λ_{max} positions for thioglycolic acid and also for 2-thiouracil (Fig. 1).

The stoichiometry of the products were confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation as shown in Fig. 2 and was found to have a 1 : 1 metal ligand ratio in the products for the both ligands. $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ (1) and thioglycolic acid were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio at pH 4.5. On slow evaporation it gives a blackish yellow product. Now the product is characterized by IR and mass spectral studies.

The IR spectra of the product in the KBr disc show strong bands at 1629, 563, 393 cm^{-1} . The band at 1629 cm^{-1} is due to the ν_{asym} (COO^-) of the metal bonded carboxyl group. Because the asymmetric COO^- stretching frequency (ν_{asym}) of the acid occurs at 1580–1660 cm^{-1} , when the group is coordinated to metal, where as a non coordinated COO^- group has the ν_{asym} (COO^-) stretching at lower frequencies²². The absorption band at 1629 cm^{-1} is therefore due to the ν_{asym} (COO^-) of the metal bonded carboxyl group, i.e. COO^- group of thioglycolic acid involved in bonding with metal. The band at 563 cm^{-1} appears due to Ru-O stretching frequency²². This fact indicates that ruthenium oxygen bond (Ru-O) is present in the final product complex. The band at 393 cm^{-1} indicates metal sulfur (Ru-S) bond is present in the final product (2), which is also supported by the fact that there is no peak at near $\sim 2500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (stretching frequency of free

Fig. 1. Spectra of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ (1), ligand (tgaH^-) substituted complex (2) and ligand (tuc) substituted complex (3); $[(1)] = 2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{tgaH}^-] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{tuc}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; pH = 4.5.

Fig. 2. Job's plot of complex (1) with thioglycolic acid.

-SH group) in the final product complex but the IR spectra of free ligand (tgaH₂) displays a sharp peak near ~2500 cm⁻¹ assignable to free -SH group. The spectrum suggests that the final product (2) is an (O, S) coordinated chelate and the thioglycolic acid behaves as bidentate ligand.

Similarly from IR spectroscopy it is also confirmed

that the product (3) bonded with 2-thiouracil through N and S atom. As the peaks at 397 and 626 cm⁻¹ indicates Ru-S and Ru-N respectively²³. The IR spectrum of the product also shows prominent bands at 1002 cm⁻¹. The C=S stretching of the non bonded 2-thiouracil occurs at 1020 cm⁻¹ which shifted 18 cm⁻¹ downwards to 1002 cm⁻¹ indicate the coordination of C=S group Ru²⁺ ion, through 'S' atom. The spectrum suggests that the final product is an (N, S) coordinated chelate and the 2-thiouracil behaves as bidentate ligand.

The conductance measurement also reveals that bonding occurs through O and S end of the thioglycolic acid ligand. During chelation, one proton is released from the -SH group of thioglycolic acid which is supported by the increase in conductance with the forwardness of the reaction. As the affinity of ruthenium(II) for sulfur donor centre is high that provides the driving force for the deprotonation in the second step.

It is clear from the mass spectrum (Fig. 3) that the ion at *m/z* ~271 has become the molecular ion species in the mixture solution and this is attributed to (thioglycolate anion + Ru^{II} + 2bipy + 2H⁺ + 2H₂O)²⁺. The precu-

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum for (2).

sor ion is shown in Fig. 4. The peak at ~ 233 and ~ 217 is due to $(\text{Ru}^{\text{II}} + 2\text{bipy} + 3\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ and $(\text{Ru}^{\text{II}} + 2\text{bipy} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ respectively.

Fig. 4. Plausible structure of the molecular ion peak from the ESI-mass spectra for (2).

It is clear from the mass spectrum (Fig. 5) that the ion at $m/z \sim 280$ has become the molecular ion species in the mixture solution and this is attributed to $(\text{Thiouracil anion} + \text{Ru}^{\text{II}} + 2\text{bipy} + \text{H}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$. The precursor ion is shown in Fig. 6. The peak at ~ 271 and ~ 217 is due to $(\text{Thiouracil anion} + \text{Ru}^{\text{II}} + 2\text{bipy} + \text{H}^+)^{2+}$ and $(\text{Ru}^{\text{II}} + 2\text{bipy} + \text{H}_2\text{O})^{2+}$ respectively.

Kinetic studies :

The kinetics measurements were carried out on a

Shimadzu UV1601 spectrophotometer attached to a thermoelectric cell temperature controller (TCC 240A) at 480 nm for thioglycolic acid where the spectral difference between the reactant complex and product (2) is large. Before each kinetic run the pH of each reactant complex and ligand was adjusted to 4.5 and a pseudo-first order conditions were employed throughout. Plots of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ against time (t) gave the rate constants $k_{2(\text{obs})}$, where A_t and A_∞ are the absorbances at time t and at infinite time respectively (Fig. 7). The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values were calculated graphically (Figs. 7 and 8) using the method of Wye and Hamm²⁴ and other calculations were done using Origin software. The rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs are reproducible within $\pm 4\%$. Similar procedure was used for ligand 2-thiouracil but in increasing mode of absorbance.

Results and discussion

The pK_1 and pK_2 values^{25,26} of thioglycolic acid and 2-thiouracil are 3.58, 7.75 and 9.78, 12.7 respectively at 25 °C. Thus at pH 4.5, the first ligand exists mainly as anion whereas second one in neutral form.

Fig. 5. Mass spectrum for (3).

Fig. 6. Plausible structure of the molecular ion peak from the ESI-mass spectra for (3).

Fig. 7. Typical plot of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time (t). $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+} = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{tgaH}^-] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.5$, temperature = 60°C .

Fig. 8. Plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus time (t) for tgaH^- .

On the other hand first acid dissociation equilibrium of the complex, $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ is 8.9^{27} .

Thus we see that in the studied pH range the complex does not change its protonation state. The effect of pH was studied and it was observed that the k_{obs} values at fixed complex concentration (1) ($1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), $[\text{Ligand}]$ ($2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and temperature 60°C were increased slightly with increase in pH. The $10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) and $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) values at different pHs collected in Table 1. When we increase the pH, the proportion of the deprotonated forms of the complex ($[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})]^+$) and ligand (tgaH^-) increase, and the reaction rate may have a slight response to the pH variation. In order to explain the observed pH dependence it may be suggested that during the ring closure step proton liberation occurs. At a higher pH, this process would be favored, which would in turn enhance the reaction rate. Similarly on increasing pH the proportion of the deprotonated forms of ligand (tuc) increase, and the reaction rate have a slight response to the pH variation.

Table 1. $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) and $10^4 k_{2(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) values for anation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ by $[\text{tgaH}^-]$ at different pH values at constant temperature and constant $[\text{ligand}]$ and $[\text{complex}]$ concentration. $[(1)] = [1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}]$, $[\text{Ligand}] = [2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}]$, temp. = 60°C

pH	$10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$	$10^4 k_{2(\text{obs})}$
3.0	0.35	1.21
	(0.32) ^a	(0.95)
	0.53	1.34
4.5	(0.54)	(1.10)
	1.08	1.54
5.0	(0.75)	(1.25)
	1.42	1.89
6.0	(0.99)	(1.31)
	1.49	1.97
	(1.21)	(1.39)

^aThe values in bracket indicate for 2-thiouracil ligand.

In a typical run, pH measured after the completion of the reaction shows a slight decrease in pH, which requires proton release from the ligands during chelation. Notwithstanding in the present kinetic runs, the substitution reactions were therefore followed at a constant pH of 4.5 to avoid complication caused by adding an additional parameter like $[\text{H}^+]$ to the rate constant.

At constant temperature, pH (4.5) and fixed concentration of complex (1), the $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time (t) plots for different ligand concentrations indicate a two step process. The first step is dependent on ligand concentration and with increasing ligand concentration a limiting rate is reached. The second step here is independent of ligand concentration.

The rate constant for such a process can be evaluated by assuming the following Scheme 1.

where n is 1 for thioglycolic acid and 0 for 2-thiouracil

Scheme 1

Here k_1 is the anation rate constant for the slow step i.e. for the interchange of the outer sphere to inner sphere complex and K_E is the outer sphere association equilibrium constant, k_2 is the rate constant for intramolecular ring closure step.

Calculation of k_1 for Step 1 ($1 \rightarrow B$):

The rate constant $k_{1(obs)}$ for the step (1) $\rightarrow B$ was evaluated by the method of Wyeh and Hamm²⁴.

The concentrations of the ligand were varied in the range (1×10^{-3}) to (5×10^{-3}) mol dm⁻³ under the conditions of constant [(1)] (1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³), pH 4.5 and temperatures from 50 to 65 °C. The pseudo-first order rate constant ($k_{1(obs)}$) were found to increase with increase in ligand concentration and show a limiting condition which is probably due to the completion of the outer sphere association complex formation. The $k_{1(obs)}$ values are collected in Tables 2 and 3. Fig. 9 illustrates the dependence of rate on different concentrations of ligand (tgaH⁻). Considering the kinetic results, the mechanism shown below can be proposed for the anation of $[Ru(bipy)_2(H_2O)_2]^{2+}$ by LH^{n-} .

Table 2. $10^3 k_{1(obs)}$ (s⁻¹) values with different [tgaH⁻] at different temperatures, [(1)] = 1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, pH = 4.5

10^3 [Ligand] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp. (°C)			
	50	55	60	65
1.0	0.36	0.41	0.54	0.72
2.0	0.70	0.85	1.08	1.35
3.0	0.99	1.14	1.37	1.76
4.0	1.21	1.37	1.75	2.29
5.0	1.34	1.5	1.92	2.56

Table 3. $10^3 k_{1(obs)}$ (s⁻¹) values with different [tuc] at different temperatures, [(1)] = 2×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, pH = 4.5

10^3 [Ligand] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp. (°C)			
	50	55	60	65
1.0	0.22	0.31	0.44	0.67
2.0	0.39	0.54	0.75	1.12
3.0	0.53	0.76	0.98	1.45
4.0	0.65	0.87	1.19	1.64
5.0	0.74	0.91	1.32	1.82

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 K_E [[Ru(bipy)_2(H_2O)_2]^{2+}][LH^{n-}]}{(1 + K_E [LH^{n-}])} \quad (2)$$

$$= k_{1(obs)} K_E \cdot [[Ru(bipy)_2(H_2O)_2]^{2+}]_T$$

T stands for total concentration of Ru^{II}.

We can write

$$k_{1(obs)} = \frac{k_1 K_E [LH^{n-}]}{(1 + K_E [LH^{n-}])} \quad (3)$$

$$1/k_{1(obs)} = 1/k_1 + 1/(k_1 K_E [LH^{n-}]) \quad (4)$$

A plot of $1/k_{1(obs)}$ versus $1/[LH^{n-}]$ should be linear (Fig. 10) with an intercept of $1/k_1$ and slope $1/k_1 K_E$. The k_1 and K_E values are listed in Table 4.

Calculation of k_2 for Step 2 ($B \rightarrow 2$):

The rate constants were calculated from latter linear portions of the graph and are collected in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 4. k_1 and K_E values

Temp. (°C)	$10^3 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	K_E (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)
50	5.24 (1.80) ^a	74 (139)
55	5.81 (2.07)	82 (176)
60	6.55 (2.62)	91 (202)
65	7.51 (3.23)	106 (263)

^aThe values in bracket indicate for 2-thiouracil ligand.

Table 5. $10^4 k_{2(\text{obs})}$ (s⁻¹) values for different tgaH⁻ concentration at different temperatures

10^3 [Ligand] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp. (°C)			
	50	55	60	65
1.0	0.96	1.25	1.55	1.85
2.0	0.98	1.24	1.54	1.84
3.0	0.99	1.28	1.56	1.86
4.0	0.99	1.24	1.55	1.85
5.0	0.97	1.29	1.55	1.90

Table 6. $10^4 k_{2(\text{obs})}$ (s⁻¹) values for different tuc concentration at different temperatures

10^3 [Ligand] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp. (°C)			
	50	55	60	65
1.0	0.74	1.01	1.26	1.65
2.0	0.73	1.02	1.25	1.65
3.0	0.75	1.02	1.27	1.67
4.0	0.74	1.01	1.28	1.63
5.0	0.72	1.00	1.26	1.66

The step is ligand independent step and in this step ring closure is taking place. The $k_{2(\text{obs})}$ values were obtained directly from the limiting slope of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time plot for different temperatures.

Effect of temperature on reaction rate :

The activation parameters for the steps (1) → B and B → (2)/(3) were calculated from the linear Eyring plots. Fig. 11 for (1) → B and Fig. 12 for B → (2) and are collected in Table 7. The low values of ΔH^\ddagger and the large negative ΔS^\ddagger values in both the steps suggested significant associative character of the substitution process. The breaking of Ru-OH₂ bond, already present and the formation of the new Ru-LHⁿ⁻ bond are equally important. The energy required to break the Ru-OH₂ bond is partially compensated by the formation of Ru-LHⁿ⁻ bond. The significant drop in entropy values indicates that both leaving and entering groups are attached in the transition state; as a result a more compact state than the original starting situation is obtained resulting in a decrease in entropy values. From the temperature dependence of K_E values Fig. 13 for the step (1) → B, ΔH_1^0 and ΔS_1^0 values can be calculated which results in a negative ΔG_1^0 supporting the spontaneous formation of an outer sphere association complex.

Mechanism and conclusion :

The interaction of thioglycolic acid and 2-thiouracil with the title ruthenium complex proceeds via two distinct consecutive steps ($k_1 \sim 10^{-3}$ s⁻¹ and $k_2 \sim 10^{-4}$ s⁻¹). First path proceeds via an associative interchange activation and the second step is the ring closure. At the outset of first path outer sphere association complex results, this is stabilized through H-bonding and is followed by an interchange from the outer sphere to the inner sphere complex. The outer sphere association equilibrium constants a measure of the extent of H-bonding for each path at different temperatures are evaluated (Tables 2 and 3). From the temperature dependence of the K_E the thermodynamic parameters are calculated $\Delta H_1^0 = 21.4 \pm 1.6$

Table 7. Activation parameters for related system with [Ru(bipy)₂(H₂O)₂]²⁺

System	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Ref.
Thiosemicarbazide	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 25.37 \pm 1.6$	$\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -215.48 \pm 4.5$	6
	$\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 24.24 \pm 1.1$	$\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -207.14 \pm 3.0$	
Glycylglycine	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 24.36 \pm 1.5$	$\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -177.81 \pm 2.8$	6
	$\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 39.9 \pm 1.6$	$\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -157 \pm 2.8$	
Thioglycolic acid	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 19.1 \pm 1.2$	$\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -230 \pm 4.0$	This work
	$\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 36.0 \pm 1.6$	$\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -192 \pm 5.0$	
2-Thiouracil	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 32.4 \pm 2.9$	$\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -198 \pm 9.0$	This work
	$\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 43.70 \pm 2.4$	$\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -189.15 \pm 7.3$	

Fig. 9. Plot of $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ versus $[\text{tgaH}^-]$, A = 50°, B = 55°, C = 60° and D = 65 °C.

Fig. 10. Plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ against $1/[\text{tgaH}^-]$, A = 50°, B = 55°, C = 60° and D = 65 °C.

kJ mol^{-1} , $\Delta S_1^0 = 102 \pm 5 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (for thioglycolic acid) and $\Delta H_1^0 = 36.1 \pm 3.9 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^0 = 153 \pm 12 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (for 2-thiouracil) ΔG^0 values, calculated for both steps at all temperature studied, have a negative magnitude which is once again in favor of the spontaneous formation of an outer sphere association complex. There occurs the formation of five member structure of the product (in case of thioglycolic acid) by the coordination of the O^- of carboxylate group and S atom with the Ru^{II} centers. Now as electron density on O^- is greater it first attacks the ruthenium(II) centre by the removal of

Fig. 11. Eyring plot for the first step (1 \rightarrow B).

Fig. 12. Eyring plot for the second step (B \rightarrow 2).

Fig. 13. Plot of $\ln K_E$ versus $1/T$.

Fig. 14. Plausible mechanism for the substitution of aqua ligands from $[Ru(bipy)_2(H_2O)_2]^{2+}$ by thioglycolic acid (2) and 2-thiouracil (3).

one water molecule i.e. follows the k_1 path and then the S atom finishes the ring closing process. But for 2-thiouracil it may be expected that S atom follows the k_1 path and N atom finishes the ring closing process.

From a comparison of the ligands used, it can be concluded that the variation in size, bulkiness and electronic effect of the entering ligands reflect their properties as nucleophiles. The differences in nucleophilicity of the ligands are obvious and their reactivity follows the order : thioglycolic acid > 2-thiouracil. The sensitivity of the reaction rate towards donor properties of the entering ligands are in the line with that expected for an associative mode of activation. Due to the higher steric effect,

the reactivity of the ligands used, 2-thiouracil decreases which reflected in the rate constant values. A plausible mechanism is shown in Fig. 14.

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